

ICT in Education: understanding Relationship between Student Attitudes and student Learning Readiness

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ABSTRACT: ICT in education can deliver instruction, support collaboration, provide access to information, and assess learning. The use of ICT has increased due to the availability of technology. Research on its effectiveness and changes in learners' needs are in focus. However, to use ICT effectively, students must have the right attitude and willingness to learn. In creating effective ICT-based learning environments, it is important to understand the relationship between attitudes and skills. This study on students using ICT found a relationship between learning readiness and attitude influence the effective use of ICT in education.

Keywords: ICT in education, learning styles, attitude, learning readiness, correlation.

I INTRODUCTION

The role of ICT in education is recurring and unavoidable. Rapid changes in technologies are indicating that the role of ICT in the future will grow tremendously in education [1]. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has revolutionized various aspects of our lives, including education. In the field of education, ICT refers to the use of digital technology and communication tools to enhance the teaching and learning process. It encompasses a wide range of technologies, including computers, the internet, mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, and educational software. The integration of ICT in education has a profound impact on how students learn, teachers teach, and educational institutions operate. Information and communication technology (ICT) has transformed education by increasing access to learning resources and providing advanced ways to engage students. ICT tools can be used to fit instruction to individual requirements, enhance teaching strategies, address learning barriers, and promote self-awareness and metacognition among students. The integration of ICT in education has altered the learning atmosphere into a dynamic and interactive space.

[2] ICT tools provide innovative ways to engage students and enhance the learning experience. Interactive educational software, multimedia presentations, and simulations make complex concepts more understandable and enjoyable for students. Digital platforms and learning management systems facilitate communication and collaboration between teachers and students, enabling personalized and self-paced learning [3] The integration of ICT in education has transformed the traditional learning environment into a dynamic and interactive space. It has improved access to education, enhanced teaching and learning processes, and fostered collaboration and communication. By leveraging on ICT, educators can provide personalized instruction and support

students' individual needs. As technology continues to advance, the role of ICT in education is likely to expand further, shaping the future of learning and teaching. ICT encompasses a wide range of technologies, including computers, internet connectivity, software applications, digital devices, and multimedia tools. Its integration into higher education has brought about significant advancements, enhancing the quality of education, expanding access to learning resources, and fostering interactive and collaborative learning environments

II LITERATURE REVIEW

Reference [4] stated that Students are more likely to have positive attitudes towards ICT in education when they perceive it as useful and relevant to their learning goals. If students see ICT tools as enhancing their understanding, engagement, and achievement, they are more likely to have favorable attitudes.

The ease with which students can use ICT tools and technologies can also affect their attitudes. If students find ICT tools user-friendly, intuitive, and accessible, they are more likely to have positive attitudes toward using them in their educational experiences [5]. Student characteristics such as prior experience and confidence in using technology can influence their attitudes towards ICT in education. Students who have had positive experiences with technology and feel competent in using it are more likely to have favorable attitudes toward ICT integration in the classroom [6].

Support and training provided by teachers in integrating ICT into the learning process can significantly impact student attitudes. When teachers are skilled, confident, and enthusiastic about using ICT, it can positively influence students' perceptions and engagement with technology [7]. The availability of reliable ICT infrastructure, including hardware, software, and internet connectivity, can influence student attitudes towards ICT in education. If students face barriers in accessing and using technology due to inadequate infrastructure, it can negatively impact their attitudes and engagement [8].

Learning readiness fosters higher levels of engagement in the classroom. Students who are ready to learn actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, and seek clarification. They are more likely to be attentive, motivated, and intrinsically interested in the subject matter, resulting in deeper learning experiences [9]. Learning readiness is associated with the development of self-regulation skills, such as goal setting, time management, and self-monitoring. Students who are ready to learn are better able to regulate their learning behaviors, set appropriate goals, and allocate sufficient time and effort to their studies, which positively

impacts their academic performance [10]. The study also found that there was a difference in attitude towards the use of VLE with respect to their technical background (i.e. technical/ non-technical) and no Readiness difference to adopt VLE in their learning. A significant relationship exists between readiness learning styles. this study emphasized more on learning styles [11].

III METHODOLOGY

A Objectives of the Study

- i. To assess students' attitudes and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.
- ii. To determine the gender difference in students' attitudes and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.
- iii. To examine the difference between undergraduate and Post Graduate students' attitudes and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.
- iv. To examine the difference between Technical and Non - Technical students' attitudes and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.
- v. To examine the difference between Urban and Rural region students' attitudes and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.
- vi. To find out the relationship between students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.

B Hypothesis

H1: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of male and female students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

H2: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of PG and UG students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

H3: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of Technical and Non-Technical students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

H4: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of Urban and Rural Region students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

H5: There is no significant relationship between students' attitude to and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.

C Sample Selection

A convenience sampling method was employed to collect data. UG, PG Students of various colleges who were using/used any form of ICT in their education. A structured questionnaire was distributed through emails. 280 filled forms returned. After initial data screening only 243 responses were found to be suitable and usable. The respondents aged between 20 to 25 with an average age of 21 years.

D Tools used for the study

A questionnaire having two scales - attitude and learning readiness towards ICT usage for learning in addition to a few demographic questions is used. A modified version (Miller's 1995) of the attitude scale is used to assess the students' attitudes toward the use of ICT for their learning. The instrument has '11' statements. Five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), was used to collect the response options. The instrument's Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.853. The Cronbach alpha is used as the reliability core of the scales [12] recommended that alpha should be at least 0.70 for all social sciences research. The internal reliability of the scales is found to be satisfactory for the collected data.

Student levels of learning readiness were measured using the modified scale developed by Hung et al (2010). The five factors of the scale are computer/internet self-efficacy, self-directed learning, learner control, learning motivation, and online communication self-efficacy. The five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), was used to collect the response options. The instrument's internal consistency in the form of Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.962 [13]

E Data analysis

TABLE 1: MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARD ICT UTILISATION IN THEIR LEARNING

	TOT AL	ME AN	STD EV
Learning through ICT-based instruction is convenient	243	3.70	0.94
ICT-based courses allow me to control the pace of my learning	243	3.65	0.99
V LE-based courses should be utilized more often to deliver instruction	243	3.57	1.01
I will recommend ICT-based courses to my friends	243	3.68	1.03
ICT-enabled courses provide me with learning opportunities that I otherwise would not have had	243	3.43	1.02
I enjoy learning from the lessons using ICT	243	3.63	0.96
I will enroll in another course offered through ICT	243	3.63	0.97
I feel isolated as a student when I take courses via the web through ICT	243	3.16	1.12
I would not have taken ICT-based courses if I had some other means of acquiring course credit	243	2.95	0.98
I prefer Web-based courses to traditional classroom instruction	243	2.96	1.037
Learning using ICT-enabled courses is boring	243	2.49	1.107

The results of the above table reveal that 60 % of the students feel that Learning through ICT-based instruction is convenient. 63% of the students feel that ICT-based courses allow them to control the pace of their learning. 62% of the students support the statement V LE-based courses should be utilized more often to deliver instruction. 59% of the students are willing to recommend ICT-based courses to their friends. 51% of students feel that ICT-enabled courses provide them with learning opportunities that they otherwise would not have had. 61% of the students said that they enjoy learning from the lessons using ICT. 60% of the students wish to enroll in another course offered through ICT. 39% of the students feel isolated as a student when they take courses via ICT. 51% do not feel isolated. 27% of the students stated that they would not have taken ICT-based courses if they had some other means of acquiring course credit. Only 34% of the students prefer Web-based courses to traditional classroom instruction. 50% of the students feel that Learning using ICT-enabled courses is boring.

TABLE 2: MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF STUDENTS' READINESS FOR ICT USE FOR THEIR LEARNING.

	TOT AL	ME AN	STD EV
Self-efficacy			
I feel confident in performing the basic functions of ICT.	243	3.59	0.89
I feel confident in my knowledge and skills of how to manage software for learning through ICT.	243	3.62	0.92
I feel confident in using the Internet to find or gather information for learning using ICT	243	3.65	1.17
Self-directed Learning			

I carry out my own study plan using ICT based Instructions	243	3.49	0.98
I seek assistance when I face learning problems, while using ICT	243	3.46	1.049
I manage time well using ICT.	243	3.48	1.069
I set up my learning goals.	243	3.69	1.073
I have higher expectation	243	3.57	1.066
<i>Learning Control</i>			
I can direct my own learning progress.	243	3.46	1.060
I am not distracted by other online activities when learning online through ICT	243	3.03	1.257
I repeat the ICT based instructional materials on the basis of my needs.	243	3.58	0.960
<i>Learning Motivation</i>			
I am open to new ideas, while using ICT	243	3.72	1.05
I have motivation to learn through ICT	243	3.54	0.99
I improve from my mistakes, while using ICT	243	3.65	1.07
I like sharing my ideas with others through ICT	243	3.57	1.05
<i>Online Communication Self-efficacy</i>			
I feel confident in using ICT to effectively communicate with others	243	3.48	1.04
I feel confident in expressing myself (emotions and humor) through ICT	243	3.41	1.05
I feel confident in posting questions in online discussions through ICT	243	3.44	1.02

The results of the above table reveal the learning readiness among UG, PG students who use/use ICT for their learning. The mean score for the statements on self – selfefficiency states that the student feels confident while performing the basic functions of ICT, confident in their knowledge and skills on how to manage software for learning through ICT, confident while using the Internet to find or gather information for their learning using ICT is found to be 3.5 with a standard deviation of 0.97. indicates that most of the students have the ability to use ICT for their learning.

The mean score of 3.6 indicates that most of the students are self-directed for their learning using ICT the statements in the second dimension state that students can carry out their own study plan using ICT based Instructions, students manage their time well using ICT, set their own goals, 50% of the students are ready to seek assistance when they face learning problems while using ICT. Most of the students have higher expectations for their learning through ICT.

The statements that they can direct their own learning progress, not get distracted by other online activities when learning online through ICT, and repeatedly use the material for their learning needs have a mean score above 3 indicating that most of the students have the ability to take charge of their learning while using ICT.

For the statements that the student is open to new ideas, has the motivation to learn, tries to improve from mistakes, and also likes to share their ideas with others while using ICT for their education under the dimension learning motivation have a mean score of 3.73 indicating most of the students are interested in learning new things using ICT.

An average score of 3.4 indicates students agree that they are confident in using ICT to effectively communicate with others expressing themselves (emotions and humor) while posing questions in online discussions through ICT.

Overall, the results reveal that the students have a positive readiness to use ICT for their learning but also require additional support.

H1: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of male and female students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

TABLE 3: MEAN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE STUDENTS' ATTITUDE AND LEARNING READINESS TO USE ICT FOR LEARNING.

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig
learning readiness	Male	115	3.5005	.79009	.510	241	.611
	Female	128	3.5538	.83536			
Attitude	Male	115	3.3684	.63085	.221	241	.826
	Female	128	3.3501	.65507			

The result reveal that [t(241)=0.51, p>0.05] the learning readiness of students in using ICT for their learning does not differ significantly with respect to their gender.

The result reveal that [t(241)=0.221, p>0.05] the attitude of students for using ICT for their learning does not differ significantly with respect to their gender.

H2: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of PG and UG students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

TABLE 4: MEAN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PG AND UG STUDENTS' ATTITUDE AND LEARNING READINESS TO USE ICT FOR LEARNING.

Variables	Studying in	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig.
Attitude	PG	130	3.3685	.65402	.253	241	.800
	UG	113	3.3475	.63162			
learning readiness	PG	130	3.6179	.82254	1.847	241	.066
	UG	113	3.4258	.79310			

The above table shows that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of PG and UG students on ICT utilisation in their learning

The result reveals that [t(241)=0.253, p>0.05] the attitude of students in using ICT for their learning does not differ significantly with respect to different education levels with a mean value of 3.3 and a standard deviation of .64.

The result reveals that [t(241)=0.1.85, p>0.05] the learning readiness of students for using ICT for their learning does not differ significantly with respect to different education levels with a mean value of 3.56 and a standard deviation of .84.

H3: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of Technical and Non-Technical students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

TABLE 5: MEAN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TECHNICAL AND NON-TECHNICAL STUDENTS' ATTITUDE AND LEARNING READINESS TO USE ICT FOR LEARNING.

Variables	Academic Background	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Df	Sig
Attitude	Technical	77	3.3743	.56523	.256	239	.799
	Non-Technical	164	3.3514	.68094			
learning readiness	Technical	77	3.5368	.75835	.134	239	.894
	Non-Technical	164	3.5217	.84401			

The result reveals that [p>0.05] the learning readiness and the attitude of students in using ICT for their learning does not differ significantly with respect to their Academic Background.

H4: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of Urban and Rural Region students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

TABLE 6: MEAN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL REGION STUDENTS' ATTITUDE AND LEARNING READINESS TO USE ICT FOR LEARNING.

Variable	Belongs to R / U Region	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Df	Sig
Attitude	U Region	186	3.2967	.69331	-2.575	237	.011
	R Region	53	3.5523	.37814			
learning readiness	U Region	186	3.4367	.85325	-3.561	237	.000
	R Region	53	3.8784	.54933			

Significant 0.05 level.

The above table shows that there is significant difference in the mean attitude scores and learning readiness of Urban and Rural Region students on ICT utilisation in their learning.

The result reveals that $[t(237) = -2.575, p < 0.05]$ the attitude of students in using ICT for their learning differ significantly with respect to the region they belong to with a mean score of 3.3 for urban region and a 3.6 mean score for rural region and standard deviation of .7 for urban region and .4 for rural region.

The result reveals that $[t(237) = -3.575, p < 0.05]$ the learning readiness of students in using ICT for their learning differs significantly with respect to the region they belong to with a mean score of 3.4 for the urban region and 3.9 mean scores for rural region and standard deviation of .8 for the urban region and .5 for rural region. Rural region students have a more positive attitude and learning readiness for utilising ICT for their learning.

H5: There is no significant relationship between students' attitudes and readiness for using ICT for their learning.

TABLE 7: PEARSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION SHOWING RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TO, AND READINESS FOR USING ICT FOR THEIR LEARNING.

Correlations			
Variables		Attitude	learning readiness
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.795**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	243	243
learning readiness	Pearson Correlation	.795**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	243	243

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above results show that there is a significant relationship between students' attitude to and readiness for using ICT in their learning (0.000; $p < 0.05$). The two variables are highly correlated with a value of 0.795. This means that the positive attitudes of students towards ICT usage will have an effect on their readiness for learning through ICT platforms.

IV FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The study assesses students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning and to determine the gender difference of students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning, and examine the difference between undergraduate and Post Graduate students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning, examine the difference between Technical and Non - Technical students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning, examine the difference between Urban and Rural region students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning, and to find out the relationship between students' attitude and readiness for ICT utilisation in their learning.

The study reveals that 60 % of the students feel that Learning through ICT-based instruction is convenient. 63% of the

students feel that ICT-based courses allow them to control the pace of their learning. 62% of the students support the statement V LE-based courses should be utilized more often to deliver instruction and only 13% of the students are not in favor of usage. 59% of the students are willing to recommend ICT-based courses to their friends. 41% of the students does not wish to recommend ICT-based courses to their friends 51% of students feel that ICT-enabled courses provide them with learning opportunities that they otherwise would not have had. 61% of the students said that they enjoy learning from the lessons using ICT. 60% of the students wish to enroll in another course offered through ICT. Most of the students feel that Learning using ICT-enabled courses is boring. Students want interaction with their peers.

V CONCLUSION

Students' attitude and learning readiness to use ICT for learning is not influenced by the gender and academic levels of the student. Undergraduate students are not so inclined towards ICT usage. As PG students have more maturity they seem to have more inclination towards responsible usage of time and resources using ICT. Technology ease is not a barrier to using ICT for learning purposes as both technical and non-technical background students show no difference in their attitude and readiness.

Students from rural backgrounds are more inclined towards learning through ICT platforms we need to emphasize providing infrastructure to all.

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